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Research Article

**QUANTITATIVE ESTIMATION OF ESOMEPRAZOLE AND
ITOPRIDE IN TABLET DOSAGE FORMS BY RP-HPLC
METHOD****Malge Priyanka, Alivelu Samala*, Dr.D. Venkata Ramana, Dr. Gadipally Sai Kiran.**¹Department Of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Holy Mary Institute Of Technology And Science
(College Of Pharmacy), Kondapur Telangana.**Article Received: July 2024****Accepted: August 2024****Published: September 2024****Abstract:**

A simple, rapid, and robust RP-HPLC method have been developed and validated to measure Esomeprazole and Itopride at wavelength (260 nm). A isocratic elution of samples performed on Symmetry C₁₈ (4.6 mm × 250 mm particle size 5 μm) column with mobile phase consisting Acetonitrile: methanol (60:40%v/v) delivered at flow rate 0.9 ml/min. A good linear response was achieved over the range of 5-50 μg/ml, respectively. The method was quantitatively evaluated in terms of system suitability test, linearity, precision, accuracy (recovery) and robustness as per standard guidelines. The method is simple, convenient and suitable for the analysis of Esomeprazole and Itopride in bulk drug.

Keywords: *Esomeprazole and Itopride, RP-HPLC, Validation, Precision, Robustness, ICH Guidelines.***Corresponding author:****Alivelu samala,**

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INTRODUCTION:

High-pressure liquid-solid chromatography (HPLC) is rapidly becoming the method of choice for separations and analysis in many fields. Almost anything that can be dissolved can be separated on some type of HPLC column. However, with this versatility come the necessity to think about the separation desired and the best way to achieve it. Changing the column, flow rate and solvent lets you change the separation and the amount of sample you can inject. HPLC is a versatile, powerful, but basically simple separation tool. It is also a time machine that can speed up your research and, thereby, allow you to do many things not possible with slower techniques. It is both an analytical and a preparative machine.

Your HPLC success depends on three things:

1. The suitability of the equipment you buy,
2. Your ability to keep it up and running (or find someone to service it) and
3. The support you receive, starting out in new directions or in solving problems that come up.

Principle:

The principle is that a solution of the sample is injected into a column of a porous material (stationary phase) and a liquid (mobile phase) is pumped at high pressure through the column. The separation of sample is based on the differences in the rates of migration through the column arising from different partition of the sample between the stationary and mobile phase. Depending upon the partition behavior of different components, elution at different time takes place.

Hplc system:

Typical HPLC system consists of the following main components:

Solvent Reservoirs: Storage of sufficient amount of HPLC solvents for continuous operation of the system. Could be equipped with an online degassing system and special filters to isolate the solvent from the influence of the environment.

Pump: This provides the constant and continuous flow of the mobile phase through the system; most modern pumps allow controlled mixing of different solvents from different reservoirs.

Injector: This allows an introduction (injection) of the analytes mixture into the stream of the mobile phase before it enters the column; most modern injectors are autosamplers, which allow programmed injections of different volumes of samples that are withdrawn from the vials in the autosampler tray.

Column: This is the heart of HPLC system; it actually produces a separation of the analytes in the mixture. A column is the place where the mobile phase is in

contact with the stationary phase, forming an interface with enormous surface. Most of the chromatography development in recent years went toward the design of many different ways to enhance this interfacial contact.

Detector: This is a device for continuous registration of specific physical (sometimes chemical) properties of the column effluent. The most common detector used in pharmaceutical analysis is UV (ultraviolet), which allows monitoring and continuous registration of the UV absorbance at a selected wavelength or over a span of wavelengths (diode array detection). Appearance of the analyte in the detector flow-cell causes the change of the absorbance. If the analyte absorbs greater than the background (mobile phase), a positive signal is obtained.

Data Acquisition and Control System: Computer-based system that controls all parameters of HPLC instrument (eluent composition (mixing of different solvents); temperature, injection sequence, etc.) and acquires data from the detector and monitors system performance (continuous monitoring of the mobile-phase composition, temperature, backpressure, etc.).

Nature of sample:

Before beginning method development, we need to review what is known about the sample.

- Number of compounds present
- Chemical structure of compound
- Molecular weights of compounds
- pKa values of compounds
- UV spectra of compound
- Concentration range of compounds in samples of interest
- Sample solubility

For Method development one has to study the physical properties like solubility, polarity, pKa and pH of the drug molecule. Polarity is a physical property of a compound. It helps an analyst, to decide the solvent and composition of the mobile phase. In a nonpolar covalent bond, the electrons are shared equally between two atoms. A polar covalent bond is one in which one atom has a greater attraction for the electrons than the other atom.

The solubility of molecules can be explained on the basis of the polarity of molecules. Polar, e.g. water, and nonpolar, e.g. benzene, solvents do not mix. In general, like dissolves like i.e., materials with similar polarity are soluble in each other. Selection of diluents is based on the solubility of analyte. The analyte must be soluble in the diluents and must not react with any of the diluent components. The diluent should match to the starting eluent composition of the assay to ensure

that no peak distortion will occur, especially for early eluting components. pH and pKa plays an important role in HPLC method development. The pH value is defined as the negative of the logarithm to base 10 of the concentration of the hydrogen ion.

$$\text{pH} = -\log_{10}[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]$$

The acidity or basicity of a substance is defined most typically by the pH value. Selecting a proper pH for ionizable analytes often leads to symmetrical and sharp peaks in HPLC. Sharp, symmetrical peaks are necessary in quantitative analysis in order to achieve low detection limits, low relative standard deviations between injections, and reproducible retention times. The acidity of an aqueous solution is determined by

$$\text{Keq} = \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+][\text{A}^-]}{[\text{H}_2\text{O}][\text{HA}]}$$

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Instruments used:

HPLC from WATERS Alliance 2695 separation module, Software: Empower 2, 996 PDA Detector.

Chemicals used:

Esomeprazole and Itopride from Sura Pharma Labs, Water and Methanol for HPLC from LICHROSOLV (MERCK), Acetonitrile for HPLC from Merck.

Hplc method development:

Trails:

Preparation of standard solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Esomeprazole and Itopride working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Methanol and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the same Methanol. Further pipette 0.15ml of the Esomeprazole and 0.3ml of the Itopride stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Methanol.

Procedure:

Inject the samples by changing the chromatographic conditions and record the chromatograms, note the conditions of proper peak elution for performing validation parameters as per ICH guidelines.

the concentration of $[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]$ ions. Thus, the pH of a solution indicates the concentration of hydrogen ions in the solution. The concentration of hydrogen ions can be indicated as $[\text{H}^+]$ or its solvated form in as $[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]$ whose value normally lies between 0 and 14. The lower the pH, the more acidic is the solution. The pH of a solution can be changed simply by adding acid or base to the solution. The pKa is characteristic of a particular compound, and it tells how readily the compound gives up a proton. An acid dissociation constant is a particular example of equilibrium constant. For the specific equilibrium between a monoprotic acid, HA and its conjugate base A^- , $\text{HA} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{A}^- + \text{H}_3\text{O}^+$ The position of equilibrium is measured by the equilibrium constant, Keq.

Validation:

Preparation of mobile phase:

Preparation of mobile phase:

Accurately measured 400ml (40%) of Water, 600ml of Acetonitrile (60%) were mixed and degassed in digital ultrasonicator for 10 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

Temperature	:	36°C	
Column	:	Symmetry	C18
(4.6×250mm) 5 μ			
Mobile phase	:	Acetonitrile:	
Water (60:40v/v)			
Flow rate	:	0.9ml/min	
Wavelength	:	260nm	
Injection volume	:	10 μ l	
Run time	:	6 min	

Fig:- Results of Optimized Chromatogram

Table:- Peak Results for Optimized Condition

S. No.	Peak name	R _t	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP plate count
1	Esomeprazole	2.781	2774027	299752		1.2	6314
2	Itopride	4.048	2533532	210321	4.6	1.3	5521

Observation: From the above chromatogram it was observed that the Esomeprazole and Itopride peaks are well separated and they shows proper retention time, resolution, peak tail and plate count. So it's optimized trial.

Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)

Figure:- Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)

Table:- Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)

S. No.	Peak Name	R _t	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP plate count
1	Esomeprazole	2.773	2770123	282157		1.6	5011
2	Itopride	4.065	2522041	251068	3.3	1.5	5947

Acceptance Criteria:

- Resolution between two drugs must be not less than 2.
- Theoretical plates must be not less than 2000.
- Tailing factor must be not less than 0.9 and not more than 2.

- It was found from above data that all the system suitability parameters for developed method were within the limit.

Assay (Standard):**Table:- Peak Results For Assay Standard Of Esomeprazole**

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Esomeprazole	2.782	2762937	357421	1.3	6344.7
2	Esomeprazole	2.766	2774613	388745	1.3	6344.2
3	Esomeprazole	2.767	2762937	399854	1.3	6300.1
4	Esomeprazole	2.795	2774613	386542	1.3	6344.7
5	Esomeprazole	2.768	2776429	364121	1.3	6344.2
Mean			2770306			
Std. Dev.			6767.495			
% RSD			0.2			

Table:- Peak Results For Assay Standard Of Itopride

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Itopride	4.049	2540214	236741	4.6	1.3	5937.7
2	Itopride	4.025	2541284	226745	4.7	1.3	5008.8
3	Itopride	4.029	2534375	210326	4.6	1.3	5937.7
4	Itopride	4.067	2526189	226741	4.7	1.3	5008.8
5	Itopride	4.030	2546248	231494	4.7	1.3	5990.7
Mean			2537662				
Std. Dev.			7677.647				
% RSD			0.3				

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2.
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is suitable.

Assay (Sample):**Table:- Peak Results For Assay Sample**

S.No.	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	Esomeprazole	2.764	2732203	294531		1.3	6314	1
2	Itopride	4.012	2507543	216321	4.6	1.3	5954	1
3	Esomeprazole	2.767	2751843	286473		1.3	6369	2
4	Itopride	4.016	2509101	216354	4.6	1.3	5944	2
5	Esomeprazole	2.764	2744776	312684		1.3	6329	3
6	Itopride	4.013	2515628	206571	4.6	1.3	5990	3

$$\%ASSAY = \frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

The % purity of Esomeprazole in pharmaceutical dosage form was found to be 100.9%.

Linearity

Chromatographic data for linearity study:

Esomeprazole:

Concentration µg/ml	Average Peak Area
5	892464
10	1866364
15	2777423
20	3709213
25	4601317

Figure: Calibration Graph for Esomeprazole

Validation Criteria: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

Conclusion: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is -4195. These values meet the validation criteria.

Itopride

Concentration µg/ml	Average Peak Area
10	920032
20	1752782
30	2521426
40	3326009
50	4217393

Figure 6.3.4 Calibration Graph for Itopride

Validation Criteria: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

Conclusion: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 46259. These values meet the validation criteria.

Precision:

Repeatability

Table-: Results Of Repeatability For Esomeprazole:

S.No.	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing
1	Esomeprazole	2.766	2766870	294578	6684	1.3
2	Esomeprazole	2.774	2771971	286541	6347	1.3
3	Esomeprazole	2.770	2771958	302657	6674	1.3
4	Esomeprazole	2.772	2780299	293412	6451	1.3
5	Esomeprazole	2.771	2789695	283154	6678	1.3
Mean			2776159			
Std. Dev			8969.896			
% RSD			0.3			

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2.
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

Table-: Results of method precision for Itopride:

S.No.	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Itopride	4.025	2534539	193240	5761	1.3	4.7
2	Itopride	4.040	2539247	201647	5489	1.3	4.6
3	Itopride	4.032	2544661	193472	5367	1.3	4.6
4	Itopride	4.041	2548839	196475	5845	1.3	4.6
5	Itopride	4.036	2558822	201394	5347	1.3	4.7
Mean			2545222				
Std. Dev			9329.852				
% RSD			0.3				

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

Intermediate Precision:**Day 1:****Table:- Results Of Intermediate Precision For Esomeprazole**

S.No.	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing
1	Esomeprazole	2.781	2715421	294651	6647	1.3
2	Esomeprazole	2.780	2778540	284123	6781	1.3
3	Esomeprazole	2.782	2754247	274561	6984	1.3
4	Esomeprazole	2.780	2780545	281241	6475	1.3
5	Esomeprazole	2.782	2777021	286471	6647	1.3
6	Esomeprazole	2.774	2780254	294512	6489	1.3
Mean			2764338			
Std. Dev			25974			
% RSD			0.9			

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2.

Table:- Results of Intermediate precision for Itopride

S.No.	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Itopride	4.048	2506927	211541	5495	1.4	4.6
2	Itopride	4.050	2504522	206141	5694	1.4	4.6
3	Itopride	4.049	2541270	198641	5785	1.4	4.7
4	Itopride	4.050	2507885	206741	5947	1.4	4.6
5	Itopride	4.049	2504587	209487	5742	1.4	4.6
6	Itopride	4.040	2504780	193481	5914	1.4	4.6
Mean			2511662				
Std. Dev			14572.01				
% RSD			0.5				

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is rugged.

Day 2:**Table:- Results of Intermediate precision Day 2 for Esomeprazole**

S.No.	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing
1	Esomeprazole	2.764	2781856	294651	6647	1.3
2	Esomeprazole	2.759	2761510	284123	6781	1.3
3	Esomeprazole	3.015	2748811	274561	6984	1.3

4	Esomeprazole	2.773	2790831	281241	6475	1.3
5	Esomeprazole	2.765	2785112	286471	6647	1.3
6	Esomeprazole	2.764	2781932	294512	6489	1.3
Mean			2775009			
Std. Dev			16222.05			
% RSD			0.5			

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2.

Table:- Results of Intermediate precision for Itopride

S.No.	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Itopride	4.015	2536301	211541	5495	1.4	4.6
2	Itopride	4.007	2541972	206141	5694	1.4	4.6
3	Itopride	4.323	2521259	198641	5785	1.4	4.7
4	Itopride	4.065	2537081	206741	5947	1.4	4.6
5	Itopride	4.020	2549869	209487	5742	1.4	4.6
6	Itopride	4.015	2536301	193481	5914	1.4	4.6
Mean			2537131				
Std. Dev			9370.087				
% RSD			0.3				

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2.
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is rugged.

Accuracy:**Table:- The accuracy results for Esomeprazole**

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	1382603	14.0625	14.05	99.9	99.8%
100%	2777270	28.125	28.1	99.9	
150%	41448756	42.1875	42.06	99.6	

Table:- The accuracy results for Itopride

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	1306990	7.5	7.5	100	99.4%
100%	2510628	15	14.8	98.6	
150%	3777999	22.5	22.46	99.8	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (98-102%).

The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence method is accurate.

Robustness**Table:- Results for Robustness****Esomeprazole:**

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.0 mL/min	2774027	2.781	6314	1.2
Less Flow rate of 0.9 mL/min	2884521	3.327	6199	1.4
More Flow rate of 1.1 mL/min	2542012	2.516	6234	1.4
Less organic phase	2888515	3.326	6298	1.4
More organic phase	2541550	2.416	6287	1.2

Acceptance criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

Itopride:

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.0 mL/min	2533532	4.048	5521	1.3
Less Flow rate of 0.9 mL/min	2750214	5.319	5643	1.6
More Flow rate of 1.1 mL/min	2254107	3.649	5782	1.5
Less organic phase	2754017	5.318	5309	1.4
More organic phase	2215870	3.233	5580	1.51

Acceptance Criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

A simple, rapid, and robust reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the quantification of Esomeprazole and Itopride. The method utilizes isocratic elution on a Symmetry C18 column with a mobile phase composed of Acetonitrile and methanol in a ratio of 60:40% v/v. Detection was carried out at a wavelength of 260 nm. The method demonstrated good linearity over the concentration range of 5–50 µg/ml for both compounds. Validation included assessments of system suitability, linearity, precision, accuracy (recovery), and robustness following standard guidelines. Overall, this method proves to be straightforward, practical, and suitable for the analysis of Esomeprazole and Itopride in bulk drug samples.

The developed RP-HPLC method offers a reliable means for the simultaneous determination of Esomeprazole and Itopride in bulk drug substances. The use of a Symmetry C18 column with the specified mobile phase composition and operating conditions resulted in good chromatographic separation and sensitivity, as indicated by the achieved linearity and precision within the studied concentration range. The method's robustness was confirmed through systematic evaluation of various parameters, ensuring consistent performance under different conditions. With its simplicity and efficiency, this method presents a valuable tool for routine analysis in pharmaceutical laboratories involved in quality control of Esomeprazole and Itopride formulations.

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